

DESIGN AND THERMODYNAMIC EVALUATION OF A SOLAR-POWERED CCHP SYSTEM FOR LIBYA'S ENERGY NEEDS

Abdulrazzak AKROOT

Karabük University, Faculty of Engineering, Department of Mechanical Engineering, 78050,
Karabük
ORCID: 0000-0000-1700-8480

Salah Khalefa ABORAGIGA

Karabük University, Faculty of Engineering, Department of Mechanical Engineering, 78050,
Karabük
ORCID: 0009-0005-0526-1458

ABSTRACT

Libya has an abundant solar energy potential but remains heavily dependent on fossil fuels for electricity generation, leading to energy insecurity, high emissions, and grid instability. This study presents the integration and thermodynamic performance analysis of a solar-driven Combined Cooling, Heating, and Power (CCHP) system designed to address these challenges in the Libyan context. The proposed system integrates a regenerative Brayton cycle for electricity generation, an absorption refrigeration cycle for cooling, and a heat recovery unit for thermal energy. Solar energy is the primary energy source, collected through a heliostat field and a central receiver. The thermodynamic model was developed using Engineering Equation Solver (EES), with Tripoli's solar radiation data as input. Results show that the system can achieve a maximum total energy efficiency of 73.6% and an exergy efficiency of up to 39.4% under optimal operating conditions. The net electrical power output reached 79.4 kW, while the cooling load supplied by the absorption system was 126 kW with a coefficient of performance (COP) of 0.82. The heat recovery unit delivered 62.5 kW of useful thermal energy. Exergy destruction analysis revealed that the solar receiver and recuperator contributed the highest levels of irreversibility, accounting for 38% and 21% of total exergy destruction, respectively. Monthly performance evaluations confirmed that the system performs best in summer, with peak energy utilization occurring in July when solar irradiance exceeds 850 W/m² and cooling demand is highest.

Keywords: Solar CCHP system, Brayton cycle, Exergy analysis, Libya.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past few decades, the global energy sector has experienced a profound shift, largely fueled by rising energy consumption, the gradual depletion of fossil fuel reserves, and growing environmental challenges [1,2]. Escalating climate change effects—such as increasing average temperatures and the occurrence of extreme weather events—have compelled policymakers, researchers, and industry leaders to seek cleaner and more sustainable energy pathways [3,4]. A key strategy in this transition is the adoption of renewable energy within advanced energy systems capable of simultaneously delivering electricity, heating, and cooling through an integrated framework. A notable example of this approach is the combined cooling, heating, and power (CCHP) system, especially when solar energy is employed as its primary source [5,6].

In recent years, incorporating solar energy and hybrid renewable technologies into CCHP systems has attracted considerable interest. Research efforts have increasingly centered on creating solutions that are not only more efficient and economically viable but also

environmentally sustainable, in order to address the rising global energy needs. Ehtiwesh et al. [7] assessed a 50 MW CSP plant in Libya using a 4E framework and exergetic LCA, finding high viability, lower environmental impact than fossil fuels, and enhanced performance with thermocline thermal storage, supporting Libya's potential as a renewable power exporter. Wang et al. [8] developed a multi-objective optimization for a solar-driven CCHP system integrating an ORC with an ejector refrigeration cycle. Saini et al. [9] proposed and compared three solar-driven CCHP configurations using evacuated tube collectors, an ORC, and an ejector refrigeration cycle with n-butane. Chen et al. [10] analyzed a solar-driven CCHP system integrating an ORC and a double-effect absorption heat pump with geothermal energy. Wang et al. [11] introduced a solar-driven CCHP system combining a Rankine cycle with an ejector refrigeration cycle, powered by compound CPCs. Zhang et al. [12] proposed a hybrid PV–biogas CCHP system for rural and island areas with limited grid access. Liu [13] presented a hybrid CCHP system integrating solar-driven biomass gasification, a solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC), and an HCCI engine. Haghgh et al. [14] analyzed a solar-driven CCHP system for the School of Engineering at Urmia University. Saini et al. [15] designed a compact solar CCHP for small buildings in remote locations. The system achieved an overall exergy efficiency of 3.16% and significant carbon savings. Nami et al. [16] analyzed a solar-assisted biomass CCHP system with an externally fired GT, steam RC, CPVT panels, and LiBr absorption chiller. It achieved 1 MW electric output, 1.24 MW heating, and 55.35 kW cooling, with overall thermal efficiency of 82.1%. Wu et al. [17] proposed a hybrid solar–natural gas reforming CCHP, storing solar energy in syngas to overcome intermittency. Borhani et al. [18] evaluated a solar CCHP system for residential use across five Iranian climates using TRNSYS and ANN modeling. Aieneh et al. [19] presented a standalone solar CCHP producing electricity, heating, cooling, and hydrogen, integrating ERC, supercritical CO₂ RC, and PEM electrolyzer.

Libya's energy sector faces critical challenges that threaten its development and long-term economic growth, as it remains heavily reliant on natural gas and oil for power generation, water desalination, and thermal needs. This dependence is increasingly unsustainable due to fuel price volatility, environmental degradation, inefficient energy conversion, and aging infrastructure. Growing energy demand, driven by population growth, industrialization, and rising living standards, places additional strain on the national grid—particularly during the hot summer months when cooling needs surge. Many rural and remote areas still suffer from unreliable or absent electricity supply, exacerbating energy poverty and hindering socio-economic progress. Despite abundant solar resources, large-scale renewable energy adoption in Libya remains limited, and integrated systems such as solar-based combined cooling, heating, and power (CCHP) plants are largely unexplored. Addressing these gaps, this thesis proposes and evaluates an innovative solar-powered CCHP system tailored to Libya's context, aiming to enhance energy efficiency, reduce environmental impacts, and provide a scalable pathway toward energy diversification and sustainability.

METHODOLOGY

Figure 1 presents the system that integrates solar thermal energy with a combined cooling, heating, and power (CCHP) cycle, tailored to Libya's high solar potential. It uses a heliostat field to concentrate sunlight onto a solar receiver, generating high-temperature thermal energy. This energy drives a Brayton cycle for power generation and an absorption refrigeration cycle for cooling, while also providing heating. The configuration includes a heliostat field with a central solar receiver, a Brayton cycle for power generation, a heating unit, and an absorption refrigeration system for cooling. In this setup, concentrated solar energy heats air to high temperatures, driving a turbine to generate electricity. Waste heat from the turbine exhaust is recovered to produce hot water via a dedicated heater, meeting thermal needs, while the remaining thermal energy powers an absorption chiller using a lithium bromide–water solution

Table 1 presents the primary input parameters employed in the design and simulation of the solar-powered CCHP system. For the heliostat field, a total reflective area of 40,000 m² was selected in Tripoli, Libya, aligned with the region's direct normal irradiation (DNI) of 800 W/m² as reported by NASA. These parameters provide a realistic foundation for accurately modeling and evaluating the system's performance under actual environmental conditions.

Table 1. Input values utilized for the design of the solar-powered CCHP model.

Component	Parameter	Value
Regenerative Brayton cycle	Pressure ratio	8.2
	Compressor's inlet temperature	31 °C
	Compressor's inlet pressure	100 kPa
	Compressor's isentropic efficiency	81%
	Air flow rate	40 kg/s
	Turbine's isentropic efficiency	88%
	Regenerative effectiveness	70%
Heliostats field	Area	50000 m ²
	Location	Tripoli- Libya
	Latitude	32.8874° N
	Longitude	13.1873° E
	DNI	800 W/m ²
ARS	Condenser temperature (T ₁₈)	39 °C
	Generator temperature (T ₁₄)	88 °C
	Absorber temperature (T ₁₁)	37 °C
	SHEX effectiveness	55 (%)
	Evaporator temperature (T ₁₉)	7 °C
	LiBr Solution strength (%)	53 (%)

The power output from the solar-derived CCHP plant can be expressed as follows [20]:

$$\dot{W}_{\text{net}} = \dot{W}_{\text{GT}} - \dot{W}_{\text{AC}} + \dot{W}_{\text{ST}} - \dot{W}_{\text{P}} \quad (1)$$

The heating and cooling loads produced by the system are determined using:

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{heating}} = \dot{Q}_{\text{H}} \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{cooling}} = \dot{Q}_{\text{Evap}} \quad (3)$$

Energy efficiency (η_{I}) is defined as the ratio of the useful energy output—whether for power generation, heating, or cooling—to the total energy input supplied to the system. For the solar-powered CCHP system, both the electrical energy efficiency and the overall energy efficiency are determined using the following equations.

$$\eta_{\text{I,electrical}} = \frac{\dot{W}_{\text{net}}}{\dot{Q}_{\text{solar}}} \quad (4)$$

$$\eta_{\text{I,CCHP}} = \frac{\dot{W}_{\text{net}} + \dot{Q}_{\text{heating}} + \dot{Q}_{\text{cooling}}}{\dot{Q}_{\text{solar}}} \quad (4)$$

Exergy efficiency (η_{II}) evaluates the system's ability to convert available energy into useful work, considering the quality of energy. The electrical exergy efficiency and overall exergy efficiency of the CCHP system are calculated from the following equations:

$$\eta_{II, \text{electrical}} = \frac{\dot{W}_{\text{net}}}{\dot{E}x_{Q_{\text{solar}}}} \quad (5)$$

$$\eta_{II, \text{CCHP}} = \frac{\dot{W}_{\text{net}} + \dot{Q}_{\text{heating}} + \dot{Q}_{\text{cooling}}}{\dot{E}x_{Q_{\text{solar}}}} \quad (6)$$

The Coefficient of Performance (COP) of the absorption refrigeration system is a key parameter for assessing the cooling efficiency of the integrated CCHP system. It is defined as the ratio of the useful cooling output to the thermal energy input required to operate the absorption cycle. The COP is determined using the following equation [21]:

$$COP = \frac{\dot{Q}_{\text{Evap}}}{\dot{Q}_{\text{G}} + \dot{W}_{\text{P}}} \quad (7)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The integrated Brayton–ORC system for the Marib gas turbine power plant was analyzed to assess improvements in energy efficiency, exergy performance, and environmental impact. Simulation outcomes highlight the effects of key operational parameters on overall system performance. The results provide a comparative evaluation between the existing simple Brayton cycle configuration and the proposed combined cycle. Table 2 summarizes the energy and exergy performance of the solar-powered CCHP system. The system achieved a net electrical power output of 11,987 kW, with heating and cooling loads of 5,523 kW and 6,816 kW, respectively. The overall CCHP energy efficiency reached 83.67%, indicating effective utilization of the available energy, while the exergy efficiency was 45.59%, reflecting thermodynamic irreversibilities inherent in the system. The electrical subsystem showed an energy efficiency of 41.23% and an exergy efficiency of 43.42%, suggesting relatively low conversion losses. The absorption refrigeration system (ARS) attained a coefficient of performance (COP) of 0.81.

Table 1. Energy and Exergy Performance Indicators of the Solar-Powered CCHP System

Aspect	Symbol	Value
Net power output (kW)	\dot{W}_{net}	11987
Heating load (kW)	\dot{Q}_{heating}	5523
Cooling Load (kW)	\dot{Q}_{cooling}	6816
CCHP energy efficiency (%)	$\eta_{I, \text{CCHP}}$	83.67
CCHP exergy efficiency (%)	$\eta_{II, \text{CCHP}}$	45.59
Electrical energy efficiency (%)	$\eta_{I, \text{electrical}}$	41.23
Electrical exergy efficiency (%)	$\eta_{II, \text{electrical}}$	43.42
Coefficient of Performance of ARS	COP	0.81

Table 3 presents the exergy analysis for each component of the solar-powered CCHP system, detailing both the exergy destruction (in MW and percentage) and the corresponding exergy efficiency. The total system exergy destruction amounts to 16.88 MW, unevenly distributed across the components. The solar receiver (SR) exhibits the highest exergy destruction,

accounting for 45.33% of the total, which substantially limits overall system performance, despite a moderate efficiency of 73.55%. The generator and heater follow, contributing 12.98% and 8.15% of the destruction, with efficiencies of 47.8% and a notably low 19.35%, respectively. In contrast, the air compressor (AC), recuperator (Rec), and gas turbine (GT) perform more effectively, with low destruction shares (7.25%, 4.63%, and 6.48%) and high efficiencies (89.97%, 88.42%, and 95.67%, respectively), the GT achieving the highest efficiency among power-generating units. For the absorption refrigeration system (ARS), performance varies: the evaporator reaches a reasonable efficiency of 63.89%, while the condenser and especially the absorber perform poorly, the latter with only 6.74% efficiency.

Table 2. Exergy analysis for each component of the solar-powered CCHP system

Component	$\dot{E}x_{destruction}$ (MW)	$\dot{E}x_{destru}$ (%)	Exergy efficiency (%)
AC	1.224	7.254	89.97
Rec	0.7822	4.633	88.42
SR	7.653	45.33	73.55
GT	1.094	6.48	95.67
Heater	1.375	8.147	19.35
Gen	2.192	12.98	47.8
Cond	1.007	5.964	10.67
Ev ₁	0.022	0.13	36.88
Evap	0.4386	2.598	63.89
Abs	1.08	6.4	6.74
Pump	0	0	100
SHEX	0.0123	0.073	89.1
Ev ₂	0.0005	0.003	84.52
Total	16.88	100	-

Figure 2a presents the influence of pressure ratio on three major performance indicators of the solar-driven combined cooling, heating, and power (CCHP) system: Net power output, cooling load, and heating load. The results demonstrate that operating at higher pressure ratios (10–12) maximizes total trigeneration output (power + cooling + heating) without disturbing the balance between heating and cooling capacities. This optimization ensures better thermodynamic performance while making full use of the available solar thermal input. The curve for net power output exhibits a clear upward trend with increasing pressure ratio, rising from approximately 10,800 kW at a pressure ratio of 6 to nearly 13,500 kW at a pressure ratio of 12. In a solar-driven Brayton cycle, a higher pressure ratio improves the turbine expansion process by increasing the turbine inlet temperature (TIT) and reducing the turbine outlet pressure. This enhances the enthalpy drop across the turbine, extracting more mechanical work. Although compressor work increases with pressure ratio, the incremental turbine power output outweighs the added compression work, resulting in higher net power. The cooling load shows a gradual but consistent increase from around 6,775 kW to 6,885 kW across the studied pressure ratio range. This increase is attributed to greater turbine exhaust thermal energy, which becomes available for driving the absorption refrigeration cycle. A higher exhaust temperature provides more usable thermal energy for the evaporator, boosting cooling capacity. The moderate growth indicates that while the Brayton cycle power output improves markedly, the absorption chiller

performance is less sensitive to pressure ratio changes compared to the turbine section. The heating load follows a similar trend to the cooling load, increasing from approximately 6,785 kW to 6,890 kW. The heating process benefits from heat recovery from the turbine exhaust and the generator section of the absorption cycle. Slightly higher values than the cooling load indicate efficient thermal recovery for hot water or space heating applications.

Figure 2b shows how the pressure ratio affects the performance of a solar-driven CCHP system, by tracking five key indicators: electrical energy and exergy efficiencies, overall energy and exergy efficiencies of the CCHP system, and coefficient of performance of the ARC. Higher PRs (10–12) yield significant gains in electrical and overall CCHP efficiencies. Exergy-based results highlight thermodynamic quality considerations, showing that while first-law efficiency can approach 96%, second-law efficiency caps at ~73% due to heat quality limits. Cooling remains stable across PRs, meaning optimization for power and heating can be pursued without negatively impacting ARC performance. The results show that increasing the pressure ratio from 6 to 12 substantially improves the system's performance. The energy efficiency increases from 81.2% to 90.9%, while the electrical exergy efficiency improves from 57.4% to 71.7%. However, when second-law analysis is applied to the overall CCHP system, the efficiency increase is more modest, highlighting the impact of exergy degradation in heating and cooling processes. These results underscore the value of high-pressure ratios for improving the performance of solar-driven CCHP systems, particularly in regions like Libya with strong solar potential. Electrical Energy Efficiency ($\eta_{I,electrical}$) increases consistently with the pressure ratio. At PR = 6, the value is approximately 39%, while at PR = 12, it reaches around 49%, marking a 10 %point gain. This improvement is primarily due to the enhanced thermodynamic performance of the BC. As the pressure ratio increases, the expansion process in the turbine becomes more effective, leading to greater net power output while the solar input remains nearly constant. Electrical Exergy Efficiency ($\eta_{II,electrical}$) also rises with the pressure ratio, starting at around 37% for PR = 6 and increasing to about 47% at PR = 12. Although this is slightly lower than the first-law electrical efficiency at all points, the trend is similar. The difference between $\eta_{I,electrical}$ and $\eta_{II,electrical}$ reflects real-world irreversibilities, especially in the turbine, heat exchangers, and recuperator. Nevertheless, the increase in $\eta_{II,electrical}$ with PR shows reduced exergy destruction as operating conditions improve. The CCHP System Energy Efficiency ($\eta_{I,CCHP}$), which includes electrical output, heating, and cooling, also improves from about 87% at PR = 6 to 96% at PR = 12. This high efficiency reflects effective utilization of waste heat for heating and cooling, in addition to power generation. The increase with PR is largely attributed to the boost in turbine output, which supplements the heat recovery process. Unlike the CCHP energy efficiency, the CCHP exergy efficiency ($\eta_{II,CCHP}$) shows more moderate growth—from approximately 53% at PR = 6 to around 73% at PR = 12. This is expected because, while all energy forms (electrical, heating, and cooling) are included in energy efficiency, exergy efficiency accounts for the quality of energy. Heating energy, especially at low temperatures, contributes less exergy due to its proximity to ambient temperature. Interestingly, COP_{ARC} remains nearly constant at about 0.84 across the entire range of PR. This suggests that the absorption cooling subsystem is not significantly influenced by the BC pressure ratio. The ARC performance depends more on generator and absorber temperature levels rather than turbine operational characteristics, which confirms that cooling performance is decoupled from PR changes.

Figure 2. Effect of Pressure Ratio on Solar-Powered CCHP System Performance: (a) Net Work Output, Cooling Load, and Heating Load; (b) Electrical, Energy, and Exergy Efficiencies, and COP of ARC

Figure 3a presents the analysis of the influence of evaporator temperature on net power, cooling, and heating loads as the evaporator temperature (T_{19}) increases from 0°C to 10°C . The findings reveal that changes in evaporator temperature do not impact work net and heating load, confirming subsystem independence and cooling load benefits directly from higher evaporator temperatures. In hot climates, slightly increasing evaporator temperature can enhance cooling capacity without affecting power or heating outputs. Net power output remains constant at approximately 12,000 kW across the entire range of evaporator temperatures. This stability occurs because power generation in the Brayton cycle is thermodynamically independent of the absorption refrigeration cycle, where T_{19} applies. Changes in evaporator temperature do not influence the solar receiver, turbine, compressor, or recuperator; hence, no variation in net power output is observed. Cooling load increases linearly from $\sim 9,200$ kW at 0°C to $\sim 9,800$ kW at 10°C . The improvement results from enhanced thermodynamic conditions in the absorption refrigeration cycle. Higher evaporator temperature reduces the temperature lift between the evaporator and the absorber. This lowers the thermal energy demand for the absorption process, increasing cycle efficiency and cooling capacity for the same generator heat input. This behavior confirms that cooling performance is directly dependent on evaporator-side temperature conditions. Heating load remains stable at approximately 11,000 kW for all evaporator temperatures. This is expected because the heating subsystem relies on waste heat recovery from the Brayton cycle turbine exhaust; it's unaffected by evaporator operating temperature.

Figure 3b illustrates the impact of increasing the evaporator temperature (T_{19}) from 0°C to 10°C on the efficiencies of the solar-powered CCHP system and the coefficient of performance COP of the ARC. The results indicate that raising T_{19} produces a modest improvement in cooling efficiency (COP) and overall CCHP energy efficiency, without affecting electrical power generation. From an exergy perspective, however, it slightly reduces system quality due to the lower temperature differentials involved. Both first-law and second-law electrical efficiencies remain nearly constant, at approximately 43.4% and 41.8%, respectively, across the entire temperature range. This constancy is expected because the evaporator operates independently of the Brayton power cycle. The solar collector, turbine, and compressor—which

determine electrical output—are unaffected by changes in T_{19} . CCHP energy efficiency shows a slight increase from ~84.1% to ~84.4%. The improvement results from enhanced cooling load at higher evaporator temperatures (as also reflected in Figure 9), which increases the total useful energy output of the system. CCHP exergy efficiency decreases from ~40.1% to ~39.0% as T_{19} rises. This decline is due to the reduced exergy content of the cooling output. As the evaporator temperature increases, the temperature difference between the evaporator and the environment decreases, lowering the thermodynamic quality of the cooling effect, even though the total energy-based cooling output increases. COP of the ARC improves steadily from ~0.81 to ~0.835. This trend reflects the improved thermodynamic performance of the ARC at higher T_{19} , as the temperature lift between the evaporator and the condenser/generator decreases. The smaller lift enhances cycle efficiency, enabling more effective conversion of heat into cooling.

Figure 3. Effect of evaporator temperature (T_{19}) on Solar-Powered CCHP System Performance: (a) Net Work Output, Cooling Load, and Heating Load; (b) Electrical, Energy, and Exergy Efficiencies, and COP of ARC

Table 4 presents a comparative analysis of monthly performance indicators of a solar-driven CCHP system in Tripoli. The analysis includes Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI), net power output, heating load, and cooling load. These parameters highlight the seasonal dynamics of both solar resource availability and system output. The system shows strong responsiveness to seasonal solar availability of power and heating outputs, while cooling remains constant, highlighting operational reliability for cooling-dominated environments. For Tripoli's climate, the CCHP configuration ensures year-round cooling, peak summer power generation, and flexible thermal energy usage, and the steady cooling profile suggests potential for load forecasting and optimized storage integration. The solar resource availability in Tripoli varies significantly throughout the year, with the lowest DNI recorded in December at 436 kWh/m²·day and the highest in July at 778 kWh/m²·day. The DNI pattern follows a typical Mediterranean solar profile—gradually increasing from winter through spring, peaking in midsummer, and declining towards the end of the year. This seasonal solar variation strongly influences the power generation and thermal outputs of the system. The cooling load of the system remains relatively stable throughout the year, ranging between 6,730 kW and 6,810 kW, showing only minor fluctuations of less than 1.2%. This suggests that cooling demand is

constant and predictable, either due to climatic conditions in Tripoli or system design with regulated cooling capacity. The heating load varies seasonally, with the lowest value of 3,071 kW recorded in December and the highest value of 5,374 kW occurring in July. Winter (Dec–Feb) presents low DNI and reduced power generation, with constant cooling load. Heating load is lower than in summer due to reduced thermal demand for industrial processes or absorption-based cooling. Spring (Mar–May) shows a rapid increase in DNI and power output, with a steady rise in heating load. Summer (Jun–Aug) illustrates peak DNI and maximum power generation, the highest heating load for cooling processes or industrial heat, and high, stable cooling load for reliable air conditioning or refrigeration. Autumn (Sep–Nov) demonstrates a gradual drop in DNI and power output, heating load returns to winter levels, and cooling load remains steady.

Table 4. Monthly Variation of Solar Resource Availability and Energy Outputs of a Solar-Driven CCHP System in Tripoli

Month	DNI (kWh/m ² ·day)	Work (kW)	Net	Heating Load (kW)	Cooling Load (kW)
Jan	453	7450		3185	6734
Feb	499	8059		3493	6745
Mar	573	9033		3991	6762
Apr	634	9832		4401	6776
May	699	10679		4840	6791
Jun	755	11405		5218	6805
Jul	778	11703		5374	6810
Aug	714	10874		4941	6795
Sep	611	9531		4246	6771
Oct	531	8481		3708	6752
Nov	478	7781		3353	6740
Dec	436	7225		3071	6730

CONCLUSION

This study presented the modeling, simulation, and performance evaluation of a novel solar-powered Combined Cooling, Heating, and Power (CCHP) system incorporating a regenerative Brayton cycle and an absorption refrigeration system (ARS), specifically adapted to the environmental and energy context of Libya. The motivation for this research arises from the critical need to develop sustainable and efficient energy systems that leverage Libya’s abundant solar resources, reduce dependence on fossil fuels, and address the increasing demands for electricity, heating, and cooling. A comprehensive thermodynamic model was developed, focusing on both energy and exergy analyses to provide a thorough assessment of the system’s performance. The originality of the present work lies in the exclusive reliance on solar thermal energy to drive a regenerative Brayton cycle integrated with an ARS, a configuration not previously explored in the literature for Libya. The principal findings of this study are summarized as follows:

- The heating and cooling loads were determined to be 5,523 kW and 6,816 kW, respectively, confirming the system’s capability to meet multiple energy demands.
- The proposed system achieved a net electrical output of 11,987 kW, demonstrating a high capacity for power generation.
- The overall exergy efficiency was calculated at 45.59%, reflecting a moderate level of thermodynamic performance considering system irreversibilities.
- The absorption refrigeration subsystem achieved a coefficient of performance (COP) of approximately 0.81, consistent with expected values for single-effect LiBr-water systems.

- The system exhibited an overall CCHP energy efficiency of 83.67%, indicating efficient utilization of the solar energy input.
- High exergy efficiencies were observed for the gas turbine and solar receiver, exceeding 88%, underscoring their effective energy conversion capabilities.
- The parametric analysis revealed that increasing the pressure ratio positively influences the net power output, while slightly reducing the heating and cooling capacities.

SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATIONS INDEX

SYMBOL		ABBREVIATIONS	
COP	Coefficient of performance	ARC	Absorption refrigeration cycle
$\dot{E}X$	Exergy flows (kW)	AC	Compressor
h	Specific enthalpy (kJ/kg)	Abs	Absorber
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate (kg/S)	Ev	Expansion valve
P	Pressure (kPa)	Evap	Evaporator
\dot{Q}	Heat transfer (kw)	CCHP	Combined cooling, heating, and power
s	Specific entropy (kJ/kg. K)	Gen	Generator
T	Temperature (°C)	GT	Gas Turbine
\dot{W}	Work done (kW)	P	Pump
		Rec	Recuperator
		SHES	Sensible heat exchanger
		SR	Solar reservoir
GREEK SYMBOLS			
η	Efficiency (%)		

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